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New bonds in language teaching practices: interfaces between linguistic theory and teaching practice.

This issue of *Letras Raras* will be dedicated to studies that aim to provide an overview of the several possible interfaces between theoretical linguistic studies and language teaching. It is of great value that this knowledge from related areas - but not necessarily interconnected, is combined to guarantee a reflective and effective language teaching. This interface may provide a great development for language professionals - active or in training, enabling them to give new meaning to the traditional ways of teaching languages, whatever they may be. The contributions in this volume address topics such as language education, the didactics of first and foreign/additional languages, teacher training, applied linguistics, and linguistic theory.

The papers that make up this volume represent the diversity of pedagogical practices in language teaching, which is evidence of a growing transformation movement in the Brazilian educational scene. From different approaches and contexts, researchers and educators propose approaches that value students' sociocultural reality, promote critical thinking, and question traditional and hegemonic teaching models.

One of the central axes of these initiatives is valorizing the students' identity, representativeness, and desire to integrate the learner into the learning process. The first text in the dossier ***Self representation in French: identity, representativeness and desire in teaching French to children*** looks at a project to teach French to children in *Niterói*/Brazil, which proposes a teaching approach based on the students' experiences and project-based pedagogy, showing that engaging with themes close to the children's reality, such as their family, can foster both language learning and the development of citizenship. The article ***Applied Linguistics: a bibliographical review of language teaching and learning on the Franco-Brazilian border*** deals with language contact in border contexts, such as the Franco-Brazilian region, which is characterized by plurilingualism and

intense linguistic and cultural contact. The study reveals the complexity of language teaching in multilingual territories. The qualitative research shows that language teaching in this region transcends the classroom itself, as it is deeply related to the social practices and daily needs of border communities. The following paper ***Effects of Explicit Instruction on the Acquisition-Learning of French as a Foreign Language*** investigates the effects of explicit instruction and perceptual training on Brazilian learners' acquisition of French pronunciation. Based on the SLM model (Speech Learning Model), the results indicate that children perform better than adults in producing and perceiving missing vowels in Portuguese. The work reinforces the effectiveness of explicit instruction in teaching pronunciation.

Critical reflection on teaching materials is also highlighted in three articles. The first, ***Salvationism and Developmentalism: coloniality biases in an English language textbook***, presents an analysis of the English textbook *Life*, which revealed its colonial biases, especially salvationism and developmentalism. The paper shows how the material supports Eurocentric and colonial discourses, even under the appearance of neutrality, contributing to the marginalization of non-hegemonic cultural knowledge and practices. The second article on teaching materials, ***MATERIALIZING a meaningful and critical English language teaching with children: the LICOMzinho outreach project and its teaching materials proposal***, presents the teaching proposal of the *LICOMzinho* outreach project, which offers online English classes for children aged 8 to 11. Based on a critical and meaningful approach to language education, the material follows the triad Contextualization - Conceptualization - Transformation. The proposal presented in the paper considers children as historically situated social subjects, promoting foreign language teaching that links language, identity and citizenship from an early age. Finally, in the third article ***Weaving knowledge: connections between the creation of teaching materials and teaching practice in FLE***, the authors discuss the development of the material *Mode et Mots: la francophonie en style*, developed as part of the Languages-Cultures outreach project at COLTEC (UFMG Technical College). The analysis focuses on the dimensions of the context, development, and use of the material, connecting teaching practice to producing pedagogical resources aimed at teaching French as a foreign language (FLE), from a discursive and contextualized perspective.

Another recurring aspect of the studies present in this volume is the concern with teacher training, highlighting the importance of integrating theory and practice from early training as a means to promote teacher protagonism and articulation with communities. In the article ***Language teacher education for the internationalization of higher education: the potential contributions of a network of communities***, the author investigates the continuing training of English teachers in the context of the *Paraná Fala Idiomas* Program. The results show that the production of teaching materials was the formative practice that drove teacher training. Thus, it was demonstrated that it is possible to articulate theoretical and practical knowledge in order to contribute to teachers' professional development in internationalization contexts. The paper ***Extension practices: reading and writing in primary and secondary schools in Jaguarão and Arroio Grande*** focuses on developing teaching skills by linking theory and practice. The work shows the importance of bringing university and school closer together, even before the compulsory supervised practice, by reflecting on the practice carried out on the Languages course at the *Universidade Federal do Pampa, Jaguarão/RS* campus.

In the field of grammar and syntax, the papers discuss the importance on going beyond classificatory and prescriptive teaching. Four articles present approaches based on generative theory (Chomsky, 1957 et seq.) and scientific literacy, in order to promote reflection on the structure of language in a meaningful and even playful way. In ***Portuguese teacher training under the Didactic Transposition: how linguistic knowledge meets the school***, the notion of didactic transposition appears as the key to bringing linguistic knowledge from academia into the classroom, as it suggests bringing the spoken language and the language taught in schools closer together. The proposal highlights the importance of incorporating students' I-language knowledge (Chomsky, 1981) into school practices in order to promote critical and scientific reflection on the mother tongue, as opposed to the traditional normative approach. The grammatical focus of this text is the two groups of intransitive verbs (inacusative/inergative) and structures in the synthetic passive voice. The article ***“Palitávore da Predicação” and “Varal da Predicação”: proposals for the development of syntactic awareness in elementary education*** presents two pedagogical proposals for teaching grammar: the “*Palitávore da Predicação*”, aimed at the simple period, and the “*Varal da Predicação*”, for the compound period. Based on the assumptions of Generative Theory, such as the Faculty of Language and language as a

system, the activities use materials that can be manipulated and aim to develop students' syntactic awareness, as they promote a scientific and reflective approach to grammar, beyond simple morphosyntactic classification. The article Research in ***Linguistics and the teaching of Portuguese Language in dialogue: the approach of the vocative in Basic Education*** reports on an action research project carried out in an elementary school, focusing on the approach to the vocative from an enunciative-discursive perspective. Using the podcast interview genre as the core of the didactic sequence, the vocative was explored as a communicative and semiotic resource. The proposal allowed students to move from a normative conception to a functional understanding of the vocative. The pedagogical practice showed the potential of a communicative approach to teaching grammar, contributing to more reflective and contextualized learning. Also based on Generative Theory, the text ***Between theory and practice: Contributions of the Null Subject Parameter to L2 teaching*** investigates how knowledge of parametric variation between languages, in the light of the Principles and Parameters Theory (Chomsky, 1981), can contribute to L2 teaching. Based on data on the acquisition of existential sentences in English by Brazilian Portuguese-speaking children, it is observed that planned linguistic input, combined with an understanding of the parametric differences between languages, can favor teaching practice and learner performance. It also highlights the applicability of this theory in the educational context. Finally, in ***Specific learning trajectories of spelling regularities***, the author analyzes regular orthographic patterns in the writing of elementary school students, based on the Multiple Pattern Integration Theory (Treiman; Kessler, 2014). The data presented in the paper shows that, although some patterns share superficial characteristics, their learning trajectories are different. The author defends the need for teaching approaches to consider phonological, morphological, and contextual aspects for more effective teaching of spelling.

Concerning reading and writing, the studies reveal both the challenges and the possible ways of developing reading and writing competencies. The research presented in the article ***Contributions to the development of reading competence: results of an action research in the Teacher Training Course*** shows significant progress when reading strategies are explicitly taught. The research investigates the development of reading competence of students from a teacher training course at a public school in Rio de Janeiro, based on sociocognitivist theory (Koch; Cunha-Lima, 2011)

and action research. The pedagogical intervention, considering the levels of reading literacy and contextualized reading strategies, showed significant advances in the students' performance, which went from level 2 to level 4 of reading literacy. On the other hand, the teaching of writing, addressed in the paper **Teaching Writing: what evidence says**, points to five essential pillars: writing fundamentals, grammatical knowledge, coherence tools, lexical mastery, and stages of the writing process. The analysis of textbooks and meta-analyses of reading teaching strategies reinforces the need for a procedural and guided approach that aims to contribute to more effective and grounded teaching practices. The last article in this dossier, **Textual production in indigenous school education: intercultural and bilingual teaching in practice**, highlights the importance of bilingual and intercultural teaching. The article shows how pedagogical practices that are sensitive to the culture and language of indigenous peoples can promote truly emancipatory education. In addition, the authors propose the development of teaching materials aimed at teaching text production in indigenous school education, based on an experience carried out in a Guarani-Mbya community in Rio Grande do Sul. The methodological proposal is based on the socio-interactionist didactic sequence (Schneuwly; Dolz, 2004), combining indigenous knowledge with teaching practices, aiming to promote intercultural, bilingual, and emancipatory education (Freire, 2024).

Together, these research studies and teaching experiences assembled in this volume point to a vision of language teaching that breaks with homogeneous and universalist models. They advocate an education committed to the reality of the subjects, to social justice as well as to the construction of critical, plural and transformative knowledge.

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References

CHOMSKY, N. *Syntactic Structures*. Mouton, 1957

CHOMSKY, N. *Lectures on government and binding*. Dordrecht: Foris, 1981.

FREIRE, Paulo. *Pedagogia da autonomia: saberes necessários à prática educativa*. 78ª ed. Rio de Janeiro: Paz & Terra, 2024.

KOCH, I. G. V.; CUNHA-LIMA, M. L. Do cognitivismo ao sociocognitivismo. In: MUSSALIM, F.; BENTES, A. C. (Org.). *Introdução à linguística: volume 3: fundamentos epistemológicos*. 5. ed. São Paulo: Cortez, 2011.

SCHNEUWLY, Bernard. *Gêneros e tipos de discurso: considerações psicológicas e ontogenéticas*. In: DOLZ, Joaquim; SCHNEUWLY, Bernard. *Gêneros orais e escritos na escola*. Tradução de Gláís Sales Cordeiro. Campinas: Mercado de Letras, 2004. p. 19-34.

TREIMAN, R.; KESSLER, B. *How children learn to write words*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2014.